

Pword-report

Language name: **Irish (LID ???)**
Name: Thomas Goldammer
Sources: Bammesberger, A. (1983) *A Handbook of Irish*. Heidelberg: Carl Winter.
Doyle, A. (2001) *Irish*. Languages of the world/Materials 201. Munich: LINCOM.
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I Language profile

of spks: 355,000 (SIL)
affiliation: **INDO-EUROPEAN**, Celtic, Insular, Goidelic
Contact lgs.: English
Status: official language in Ireland and Northern Ireland (GB), literature language
Prospects: not really endangered
Struct. results: no data

II Morpheme types

Stem

Restricted suffix:

-(i)m '1s.PRES' (V only)

- (1) *bris-im*
break-1s.PRES
'I break'

Restricted prefix:

ni- 'NEG' (V only)

- (2) *ní-itheann Seán a dhinnéar gach lá sa teach ósta*
NEG-eats S. his dinner every day in the restaurant
'Seán does not eat his dinner every day in the restaurant.'

Semi-restricted suffix:

-án 'DIM' (N, V)

- (3) *cnoc-án* (4) *eitl-án*
hill-DIM fly(v)-DIM
'hillock' 'airplane'

Restricted phrasal prefix:

cé 'Q' (with VP)

- (5) *cé a rinne é?* 'who did it?'
cé-n=fear é? 'what man is he?' (the -n= is the cliticized article of the 'man')

but also:

an 'DEF.sg.masc.' (with NP)

- (6) *an=tslabhra* [ə=tlaurə] 'the chain'

Semi-restricted prefix:

an- 'AUG' (with A, N)

- (7) *maith* 'good' → *anmhaith* 'very good'
lá 'day' → *anlá* 'a great day'

Restricted circumfix:
in-ta '-able' (with V)

(8) pós 'marry' → *inphósta* 'marriageable'

III Syllable

A Onset-clusters

3 Consonants:
voiceless sibilant + voiceless stop + nonnasal sonorant

(9) *spleách* [spʲlʲa:x] 'dependent'
scléip [skʲlʲe:pʲ] 'gaiety'
sraith [skrah] 'layer'

2 Consonants:
voiceless sibilant + stop or sonorant

(10) *slí* [ʃi:] 'way'
sraith [srah] 'row'
scéal [skʲe:l] 'story'

stop or /f(θ)/ + nonnasal sonorant

(11) *plé* [plʲe:] 'discussion'
cnoc [krok] 'hill'
gnó [gro:] 'business'
treabhsar [trʲausər] 'trousers'
dlúth [dlu:h] 'thick'
tláith [tla:h] 'mild'
fraoch [fre:x] 'heather'

/t(θ)/ + /n(θ)/

(12) *tnúth* [tnu:h] 'expect'

/m(θ)/ + /r(θ)/

(13) *mná* [mra:] 'women'

B Nucleus

short vowel:

(14) *fanfaidh* [fanə] 'will remain'

long vowel:

(15) *mná* [mra:] 'women'

diphthong:

(16) *leabhar* [ʲaur] 'book'

C Coda-clusters

2 Consonants:
sonorant + voiceless stop

- (17) *alt* [alt] 'joint'
sonc [su:ɲk] 'nudge'

/r/ + /d(i)/

- (18) *árd* [a:rd] 'high'

/ŋ(i)/ + /g(i)/

- (19) *long* [lu:ŋg] 'ship'

sibilant + /t(i)/ or /k(i)/

- (20) *post* [post] 'post'
seasc [ʃask] 'barren'

/x(i)/ + /t(i)/

- (21) *céacht* [kʲe:xt] 'plough'

D *heterosyllabic clusters*

every possible coda-consonant + every possible onset consonant:

- (22) *gcathrach* [gah.rəx] 'city.PL.GEN'

- "Words" can begin with /ŋ/, or /ŋʲ/ → [ɲ]: ... *ngasúr* [ŋasu:r] 'boy', ... *ngeata* [ɲætə] 'gate', but **only** by eclipsis (**when preceded by special prepositions, numerals, pronouns, etc., that are proclitics**) → the lexical entries for the abovementioned words are /gasu:r/ and /gʲætə/!
- Words can begin with a vowel: *amhras* [aurəs] 'doubt'
- Function-words, but not lexical words, can be monomoraic: *an* [ə] 'DEF.NOM.sg.masc', but they are then clitic, so there is a **minimal requirement for words to be bimoraic!**

IV Tone & Stress

A *Stress*

Mostly on the first syllable (except some loans (24) or words of an unstressed clitic and a stem (25)):

- (23) *cuirim* [ˈkʲurʲəm] 'I put'
amhras [ˈaurəs] 'doubt'

- (24) *tobac* [təˈbak] 'tobacco'

- (25) *anocht* [əˈnoxt] 'tonight'

If a word has an primarily unstressed long vowel, this vowel gets secondary stress:

- (26) *bachlóg* [ˈbax,lo:g] 'bud'

B *Tone*

no evidence for tonal contrasts

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

A *Stem mutation*

In certain morphological environments, the initial consonant of a stem is changed.

For example:

The noun preceded by the article (in (27) the *an*) is lenited (stop, /m/ → fricative/glide/h, fricative → h/∅):

- (27) **bean** [bʲ...] 'woman' → *gan an bhean* [wʲ... ~ vʲ...] 'without the woman'
 but also:
 /sʲæ:n/ 'old' + /bʲæ:n/ 'woman' → [ʃæ:mʲvʲæ:n]
 /muk/ 'pig' + /fʲo:lʲ/ 'meat' → [mikʲo:lʲ] 'pork' (lenited /f/ is ∅)

Some prepositions (in (28) the *na* 'of') cause "eclipsis" (voiceless stop → voiced, voiced stop → nasal, #V → #nV):

- (28) **ban** [b...] 'woman.PL' → *cumann na mban* [m...] 'society of women'

The masc. sg. article causes t-prefixation, when the following noun has an initial vowel:

- (29) **ór** 'gold' → *gan an tór* 'without the gold'

The initial /s/ of a word is replaced by [t] in NOM.sg.fem and GEN.sg.masc. after the article:

- (30) **slat** 'rod' → *an tslat* [ə tlat] 'the rod'

Some articles, pronouns, prepositions, nouns, ordinal numbers, and other particles cause h-prefixation, when the following word has an initial vowel:

- (31) **Éirinn** 'Ireland' → *go hÉirinn* 'to Ireland'
 (32) **áit** 'place' → *an séú háit* 'the sixth place'

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

With the interrogative *cé* the article is encliticized → *cén* (cf. example (5) in section II above). No change in the application of phon. rules.

As stated in section III, most function words are proclitics, because they cause changes at the initial segment of the following word, that produce structures that cannot occur free (initial velar nasal, initial /tʲ/ etc.) (examples see section III, and also ex. (6) in section II above)

Ablaut (of vowels)/Palatalization/Depalatalization (of consonants):

- (33) NOM.sg → GEN.sg:

[spʲal] → [spʲelʲ+i] 'scythe'	Ablaut + Suffix /-ə/
[arəm] → [arʲimʲ] 'weapon'	Palatalization
[filʲ] → [fol+ə] 'blood'	Depalatalization + Suffix /-ə/
[uv] → [ivʲ+i] 'egg'	Ablaut + Palatalization + Suffix /-ə/
[gʲlʲaun] → [gʲlʲan+ə] 'glen'	Length Ablaut + Suffix /-ə/
[firʲən] → [fo:rnʲ+i] 'crew'	Length Ablaut + Ablaut + Suffix /-ə/

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

A Phonotactics

*word-initial /ŋ(ʲ)/, except when preceded by a leniting clitic (see end of section III)

*word-initial /(s)rʲ/: *rí* [ri:] *[rʲi:] 'king', *sreabh* [srav] *[rʲav] 'stream'

*word-initial /v(ʲ)/ and /x(ʲ)/, except when preceded by a mutating clitic

B Morphophonemic Rules

1. Palatalization spreading:

[+cons] → [+front] / {[+front]____, ____ [+front]} (also between two stems in compounds)

- (34) *sagairt* /sagəɾt/ → [sagəɾtʲ] 'priest'
gleann /gʲaun/ → [gʲaun] 'glen'
 /sʲæ:n/ 'old' + /bʲæ:n/ 'woman' → [ʃæ:mʲvʲæ:n]
 /muk/ 'pig' + /pʰo:lʲ/ 'meat' → [mikʰo:lʲ] 'pork' (lenited /f/ is Ø)

2. Depalatalization:

/r x/ → [-front] / ___[COR, +anterior]

- (35) *boicht* /boxʲt/ → [boxtʲ] *[boxʲtʲ] 'poor.GEN'
airne /a:rʲne/ → [a:rnʲi] *[a:rʲnʲi] 'sloe'

3. Vowel reduction:

[-cons, -stressed, -long] → [ə] / [-front]___[-front]
 → [i] / elsewhere

- (36) *bata* /bata/ → ['batə] 'stick'
airne /a:rʲne/ → ['a:rnʲi] 'sloe'

4. Vowel epenthesis

Ø → [ə] / [-front]___[-front] but only between members of disallowed coda clusters
 → [i] / elsewhere dito

- (37) /sʲelʲv/ → [ʃelʲiv] 'possession'
 /marv/ → [marəv] 'dead'

5. Nasal place assimilation

/n/ → [αPLACE] / ___+[+cons,αPLACE] (especially between morphemes or parts of compounds, within stems underlyingly likely not occurring)

- (38) /sʲæ:n/ 'old' + /bʲæ:n/ 'woman' → [ʃæ:mʲvʲæ:n] 'old woman'

IX Reduplication

not attested

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

no data

XI Other Special things

Geminates: n/a.

Foot structure: n/a.

Exceptions to rules are mentioned within the discussion of the rules.